

Quantum Mechanics Based on the Nature of Force?

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In previous notes (1), we argued that quantum mechanics follows from treating the potential in terms of certain physical units of the form $\exp(ikx)$ i.e. $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$. These deliver an impulse of momentum k . $\exp(ikx)$ has a number of properties. First, it is invariant in space as much as can be under the circumstances (periodic), secondly it is two dimensional with a modulus of 1 and thirdly, it has positive and negative portions. Furthermore, we argue that a quantum particle in a potential takes the same form i.e a distribution of $\exp(ipx)$'s i.e. $W(x)=\text{wavefunction}=\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. In other words, it also acts like a kind of potential, but it is associated with an average kinetic energy. In this note, we consider the form $\exp(ipx)$ in terms of action/reaction. The quantum particle or unit of potential delivers an impulse hit and so should be linked to the idea of action reaction which is already known in classical mechanics. There, action/reaction is considered in terms of two objects. In this note, we speculate that the quantum particle or unit of potential may already have action/reaction built-in. This would describe why $\exp(ipx)$ is periodic (i.e has positive and negative portions while still having an overall modulus of 1). It would also help explain interference. Finally, one may note, as is well known in quantum mechanics, that the form $\exp(ipx)$ leads to conservation of momentum through $\langle \exp(ip_1 x)\exp(ip_2 x) \text{ constant } \exp(ip_3 x)\exp(ip_4 x) \rangle$ i.e. a built in action/reaction $\exp(ipx)$ form is directly linked to momentum conservation.

Classical Mechanics and Action/Reaction

The idea of action/reaction is part of Newtonian mechanics, but is usually applied to different objects. For example, a particle causes an action on another, but recoils suffering a reaction itself. Classical mechanics deals with the idea of force changing the particle velocity from x point to another.

Quantum Mechanics

Quantum mechanics is very different from classical mechanics in that it deals with momentum eigenstates which are invariant in space i.e. $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. For a single eigentstate this is fine, but in the presence of a potential an ensemble of free states are used i.e. $W(x)=\text{Sum over } a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Classical statistical mechanics which also deals with free particles at each x is linked to the idea that a particle accelerates under a potential from x_1 to x_2 . This does not seem to be the scenario in quantum mechanics. Furthermore if one writes $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$ and assumes that $\exp(ikx)$ delivers an impulse hit of momentum k , one has an usual situation. On average $V(x)$ (or its force $-dV/dx$) accelerates v_{rms} from x_1 to x_2 , but $\exp(ikx)$ is invariant in space, but also has an unusual periodic nature. The picture of an acceleration from x_1 to x_2 and that of an impulse k with an x -independent weight V_k throughout x space seem contradictory. "X" dependence must be brought in in some manner so that an

average of impulses creates $V(x)$, as argued in other notes, but this does not provide a physical understanding of the periodic nature and its x dependence.

Here we suggest that action-reaction may be the underlying driving force behind $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(ikx)$. This self-action/reaction within a particle or potential unit $\exp(ikx)$ may describe the negative and positive regions of probability (if one considers $\exp(ipx)$ to be a kind of probability). In order to keep probability conserved one must introduce two dimensions i.e. use a complex probability $\exp(ipx)$.

Conservation of Momentum and Action/Reaction

Action/reaction in classical physics is usually associated with conservation of momentum. For example, object 1 imparts momentum on object 2, but receives a recoil momentum such that overall momentum is conserved. If this is the case and if $\exp(ipx)$ represents a built-in action reaction, it should be linked to momentum conservation which seems to be the case i.e.

$$\langle \exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ constant } \exp(ip_3 x) \exp(ip_4 x) \rangle = \text{delta function } [(p_1+p_2) - (p_3+p_4)] \quad ((1))$$

Consequences of Action/Reaction

A quantum free particle has a wavefunction of $\exp(ipx)$. As argued above this has a modulus of 1 at each x and if the particle does not interact in any way, the action/reaction (linked to a wavelength proportional to $1/p$) does not seem to be visualized. Experimental visualization seems to appear if some kind of reaction occurs. Furthermore, this visualization seems to be directly linked to the interactions themselves. In (2) it was noted that quantum fluctuating densities in space and time appear for both a bound state $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and for a heat bath time dependent scenario $W(x,t) = \text{Sum over } n \ a_n(E_n) \exp(-iE_n t)$. For the bound state case with $a(p)=a(-p)$ one has fluctuating cross terms in the observable spatial density (x,t) of the form:

$$\cos((p_i-p_j) x) \quad \text{where } p_i-p_j \text{ is an impulse change i.e. a change from momentum } p_j \text{ to } p_i. \quad ((2a))$$

$$\text{and for the heat bath terms of: } \cos((E_i-E_j) t) \quad \text{where } E_i-E_j \text{ is the energy of an emitted or absorbed photon/phonon etc } ((2b))$$

Thus a classical observable, namely the local spatial density, contains a background of $a(p_i)a(p_i) \cos((p_i-p_j)x)$ where $\cos((p_i-p_j)x) = \frac{1}{2} (\exp(-ip_j x) \exp(ip_i x) + \exp(ip_j x) \exp(-ip_i x))$ terms together with impulse units which are periodic through space and reveal action/reaction positive/negative density values. That is $\cos((p_i-p_j)x)$ may be positive or negative and this creates the crest/trough patterns. Thus it is not even the action/reaction mechanism built within the quantum particle (although this lays the basis for the physical effect), but the impulse changes from one momentum to another which create quantum interference effects (which may be in space ((2a)) or in time ((2b))). (Actually, ((2b)) has both space and time interference, one at the momentum p level and the other at the E energy level.)

If one considers a system with $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and examines the spatial density (for the bound case):

$$\text{density}(x) = W(x)W(x) = \sum_p a(p)a(p) + \sum_{p_1, p_2} a(p_1)a(p_2) \cos((p_1-p_2)x) \quad (3)$$

The first term describes particles with different momentum values, but now a probability of $a(p)a(p)$ seems to be used, while the second term describes interaction units which have action/reaction and create spatial crest/trough patterns.

If one were to describe the kinetic energy of the system, one might write:

$$\text{KE throughout all } x = \sum_p p^2/2m a(p)a(p) \quad (4)$$

Thus there is a spatial density at each x . It is nonuniform due to the action/reaction interference of the interaction units $\cos((p_1-p_2)x)$. At the same time there are "free" particles which create an overall kinetic energy throughout all x . Finally, there is the question of average kinetic energy at x which should be defined because $V(x)$ is defined at x . In fact, one should have the classical result:

$$\text{KE}(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad (5) \text{ where } \text{KE}(x) = [\sum_p a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx)] / [\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)] \quad (5)$$

This is an unusual result, because it uses the action/reaction interference behaviour of $\exp(ipx)$ to create a $\frac{1}{2}m v_{rms} v_{rms}$ pattern, although $\frac{1}{2}m v_{rms} v_{rms}$ does not seem to be an observable. It must be linked with density(x) (free particles $a(p)a(p)$ terms with interaction units with action/reaction $\cos((p_i-p_j)x)$ interference). This should yield the overall kinetic energy when integrated over space i.e.

$$\text{KE over all space} = \int dx \text{ KE}(x) \text{ density}(x) \quad \text{with } (3) \text{ and } (5) \text{ used. } \quad (6)$$

It seems that it is because of the interaction action/reaction units (i.e. the impulse changes $\cos((p_i-p_j)x)$) that a spatial density is created in the first place. This is very different from the spatial density which is created in classical statistical mechanics which creates pressure difference to counteract the force $= -dV/dx$. Here impulse hits have their own action/reaction pressure differences which interfere to create an overall pattern against constant spatial density: $\sum_p a(p)a(p)$ of free particles. Thus interference plays a role in describing the overall average kinetic energy seen at a point x i.e.

$$\text{Overall kinetic energy at } x = \text{density}(x) \text{ KE}(x) \quad (7) \text{ where } \text{KE}(x) \text{ is the classical result.}$$

All of these results seem to follow from the nature of the potential which is physically represented by units with action/reaction which deliver k momentum impulse hits i.e. $\exp(ikx)$. These carry non- x dependent coefficients V_k .

Conclusion

In conclusion, quantum mechanics differs from classical mechanics in a number of ways. For instance, in classical mechanics one thinks of a particle existing at $x(t)$ and a force $-dV/dx$ accelerating it from x_1 to x_1+dx_1 . Secondly, quantum mechanics seems to have crests/troughs and eliminates that idea of acceleration altogether (except for vrms which behaves classically in a bound state). The crests/troughs seem to be linked to periodicity. We argue that this periodicity, namely $\cos(px)$, represents a self-action/reaction both within a quantum momentum eigenstate and a unit of potential $V_k \exp(ikx)$ which represents an impulse hit of momentum k . " $\cos(px)$ " becomes $\exp(ipx)$ to conserve probability at each x (modulus of 1) with $\exp(ipx)$ being thought of as a kind of probability. Having action/reaction as an underlying physical idea seems to provide a physical picture for interference.

In a bound state one has a spatial density of $W(x)W(x)$. This contains $a(p)a(p)$ terms representing free particles throughout x with a probability of $a(p)a(p)$ and impulse hit units $a(p_1)a(p_2)\cos((p_1-p_2)x)$ which carry action/reaction and create the crest/trough pattern within the constant sea of $a(p)a(p)$ probability. Thus, the overall picture is one that exists throughout space, there is no acceleration from one point to another. There is a local density due to the action/reaction interference pattern of the impulse terms, but overall kinetic energy may be thought of as being created by the $a(p)a(p)$ terms i.e. $\sum_p a(p)a(p) p^2/2$ which should be equivalent to $\int dx \text{ density}(x) KE(x)$ where $KE(x)$ is the classical kinetic energy of a particle at x which is also equivalent to an unusual interference expression in quantum mechanics: $[\sum_p a(p)p^2/2m \exp(ipx)]/[\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)]$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Time Base Force (Impulse) Versus Space Based Force ($-dV/dx$) in Classical and Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Differing Space and Time Interactions in Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2021)